

RECOMMENDATIONS ON
**MINIMUM STANDARDS FOR
RESEARCH CAREERS**
2026

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Recommendations on 'Minimum Standards for Research Careers: A common approach for careers in research and innovation across the European Research Area'

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MINIMUM STANDARDS FOR RESEARCH CAREERS

**A Common Approach for
Careers in Research and
Innovation across the
European Research Area**

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Preamble

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Research is one of Europe's most powerful engines of progress. It advances fundamental knowledge, fuels innovation, and helps address the defining challenges of our time. It is sustained by a highly skilled workforce, including researchers, technicians, data professionals, managers, and others whose expertise underpins the quality and impact of European research.

As funders and performers of research, Science Europe Member Organisations play a critical role in shaping the conditions under which this workforce operates. Ensuring that research careers are attractive, equitable, and sustainable is therefore both a strategic priority and an institutional responsibility. Failure to do so risks diminishing the research workforce over time, weakening Europe's capacity to maintain competitiveness and leadership in global research and innovation.

Research careers are increasingly characterised by complexity, mobility, and diversity of roles and pathways. Professionals routinely move across disciplines, institutions, sectors, and national borders, requiring support structures that enable such mobility without creating or entrenching bias or discrimination. Competitive and coherent employment conditions, including remuneration, social security coverage, academic freedom, and access to high quality infrastructure are essential to sustaining an environment that attracts and retains talent within Europe's research and innovation systems.

In an increasingly competitive global context, Europe must actively address risks to its research workforce, including talent outflows within and beyond the European Research Area. This publication sets out how Science Europe aims to respond to these challenges through coordinated, principled action. With a membership covering research funding and research performing organisations, Science Europe is well positioned to support alignment, collaboration, and collective action at a European level.

Introduction

Common missions for Science Europe Member Organisations are the advancement of knowledge and enabling the quality and impact of research. To achieve these, Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) and Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) must adequately support talented individuals, enable inclusive, diverse, and effective teams, foster high-quality research processes, and deliver impactful outcomes (in the broadest sense).

It is, therefore, essential that careers in research (including researchers and all research professional staff¹) are both attractive and sustainable: offering an environment where individuals at all career stages can grow and develop long-term perspectives, professionally and personally, and involve themselves in rewarding and challenging working environments that foster high quality research for the benefit of all.

Research is increasingly complex and international, and research professionals are more mobile geographically, but also in terms of discipline, role, and sector.² As such, in a global context where talent is highly mobile, Europe must provide competitive, diverse, and secure career pathways to attract and retain research professionals across the plethora of roles that contribute to high quality and impactful research. This is not only key to preventing brain drain but also to supporting the next generation of research leaders who will, in turn, steer and drive research quality and impact.

At the same time, persistent career precarity, characterised by short-term contracts, fragmented career pathways, and high dependency on project-based funding, remains a structural challenge across the European Research Area (ERA) and must be addressed as a matter of priority. By strengthening career prospects for all research professionals, Science Europe members contribute directly to the resilience, competitiveness, and attractiveness of the ERA, advancing its leadership role in research and as a desired destination for talented professionals.

Supporting sustainable careers underpins the broader role and importance of research in our societies, economies, and cultures. Creating attractive and inclusive career frameworks enhances diversity and collaboration across Europe and beyond: values that are central to the research endeavour, and that in turn foster public trust in research and societal engagement. By focusing on career attractiveness, Science Europe Member Organisations can ensure that working conditions and research environments are conducive to both individual fulfilment and collective achievement, ultimately supporting European research excellence and the role of research and innovation in European life.

Science Europe is uniquely placed to offer pan-European guidance, best practice models, and recommendations on attractive careers in research as it represents a membership comprising both research performing and research funding organisations who, collectively, support all aspects and stages of research career pathways:

- **Research Performing Organisations** (including universities, research institutes, and other bodies that conduct research) are direct employers of research professionals from Ph.D. candidates, trainee data stewards, and young research managers, to professors, institutional leaders, and highly expert technicians. RPOs have a central role in enabling attractive careers in research by providing supportive employment conditions, offering clear and diverse

1. For the purposes of this document, 'research professionals' refers to all individuals contributing directly to the research and innovation system, including researchers at all career stages, doctoral candidates (irrespective of contractual status), technicians, data stewards, research managers, and other specialised research-enabling staff, whether employed directly by institutions or funded through external grants.

2. Herein, the terms 'mobile' and 'mobility' will refer to a broad concept may include geographical, virtual, inter-sectoral, inter-disciplinary, inter-role, and intellectual mobility.

career pathways, fostering positive environments and cultures, and providing guidance, support, and development opportunities.

- **Research Funding Organisations** shape the system and environment in which research careers develop. They are a connection between strategic policies and research performing organisations, funding (and collaborating with) researchers at all career stages, projects of myriad orientations, and institutions with diverse scopes and missions. Through the development and implementation of funding programmes (including associated support mechanisms), RFOs create incentives and recognition systems that can determine the attractiveness and accessibility of career pathways in research as well as the types of research that are conducted, and the actions and skills that are valued as part of the research endeavour.

Collectively, and in partnership with other research stakeholders, RPOs and RFOs share responsibility for building attractive, sustainable, coherent, yet interoperable and permeable research systems, both at national and international levels. Strategic alignment on key values and conditions, policies, and support mechanisms can help foster a more attractive research system for talented and mobile research professionals.

At the same time, diversity in the research system (referring to both diverse representation and a diversity of ideas) is a key element to the attractiveness of the ERA. Furthermore, the autonomy and freedom of national systems and individual organisations/institutes also play a key role in attracting and retaining talent in the ERA.

As such, Science Europe situates itself as a forum where both aligned and diverse approaches can be discussed and actioned according to the needs and benefits of the system. Further, Science Europe advocates these approaches towards relevant policy and decision makers, recognising that many elements are grounded and dependent upon national and EU legislation.

The myriad challenges our research system faces in offering attractive careers are well-known and well-documented. In 2024, Science Europe issued a [Challenge Statement](#) to provoke a reflection on these issues within its membership, and it subsequently [hosted a workshop](#) to gather perspectives and discuss potential actions to address these shortcomings. A common European approach to minimum standards for careers in research was identified as one key action area. The recommendations presented here offer a frame for advocacy and the establishment of minimum standards across the ERA and highlight good practices that already exist to guide implementation. The recommendations are structured according to three categories: 1) Working Conditions & Employment, 2) Research Environment, and 3) Professional Development, Well-being, and Supporting Infrastructure.

To support implementation, Science Europe will encourage and provide a forum for Member Organisations to monitor and exchange on progress towards the recommendations made, aligning with relevant ERA frameworks with a view to fostering greater coherence. The implementation of these recommendations requires coordinated action at multiple levels: European, national, and organisational, recognising the distribution of competences while promoting convergence through shared principles and voluntary alignment.

CHAPTER ONE

WORKING CONDITIONS & EMPLOYMENT

- Attractive Salaries
- Mobility
- Social Security Provisions

Attractive Salaries

Salaries commensurate with the skills, competencies, and experience of the research professionals must be provided to those employed and funded by research organisations, and long-term stability should be normal rather than exceptional.

Recommendations

- A common European approach to salary scales for various roles and career stages should be promoted, adjusted to account for differences in national costs of living and purchasing power parity.
 - Clear salary bands for different roles and experience levels should be transparently and accessibly displayed by RFOs and RPOs.
 - To attract a broader range of talented individuals, salaries for research professionals should be comparable to other relevant sectors, where possible.
- Mechanisms and instruments to improve the long-term stability of careers in research should be developed and piloted offering clear career pathway possibilities to funded and employed research professionals.
 - RPOs should consider longer-term contracts and/or connected/laddered employment opportunities.
 - RFOs should investigate opportunities for longer-term grants and linked funding programmes.

Guiding Practices

The [Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions](#) (pages 156–157) adjust their living allowance according to country-specific correction factor.

The [Dutch Research Council Talent Programme](#) offers three forms of funding (Veni, Vidi, Vici), tailored to different stages in the careers of researchers, with each form providing “meaningful stimulus for the development of their own line of research and the development of the researcher’s talents.”

Mobility

Mobility comes in various forms (inter-sectoral, inter-disciplinary, geographical, virtual, and so on). It should be carefully enabled wherever it is beneficial, with a focus on the skills and competencies gained, the research results obtained, and the outcomes achieved, such as network forming, collaboration building, and experiential learning. At the same time, mobility should not be a requirement for career progression, recognising that it is neither feasible nor opportune for all. Rather, it should be viewed as one of multiple paths to obtain the skills and competencies required for a role.

Recommendations

- Possibilities to propose various forms of mobility should be included in grant application structures by RFOs.
- Opportunities for mobility should be mentioned in hiring and promotion schemes and positions by RPOs.
- Both RFOs and RPOs should provide clear and accessible support (such as helpdesks, training resources, and guidance material) to mobile researchers and those seeking mobility opportunities.

Guiding Practices

Based on the results of a [study identifying international mobility](#) as a major obstacle of women in research at early career stages with children, F.R.S.-FNRS adopted a revised definition of mobility that recognises moves outside the home institution even within the same country or region as valuable. Aware of the biases affecting access to mobility (family constraints, financial burdens, and so on), the F.R.S.-FNRS values not only international mobility but also mobility within institutions of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation.

With 43 European countries and 9 worldwide hubs, [EURAXESS | Researchers in Motion](#) is the largest pan-European initiative to foster researchers' mobility and career development. It aims to strengthen collaboration between Europe and the global community, expanding mobility and career development possibilities for researchers worldwide.

The [Research Ireland Enterprise Fellowships](#) provide a unique national initiative to allow excellent researchers in all disciplines, based at an Eligible Research Body, to engage in collaborative research with enterprise. Partners can range from SMEs, multinational companies, registered charities, social or cultural organisations, and, where justified, public-sector agencies.

Social Security Provisions

Research professionals funded or employed by research organisations should have access to the widest array of feasible social security provisions according to function and status. These provisions should include pensions, healthcare, unemployment protection, and paid leave (where maternity and paternity leave, sick leave, and vacation leave are necessary, and other forms of leave such as bereavement leave, care of elderly or disabled relatives, and military leave are highly desirable), aiming to ensure income security and access to essential public services for all research professionals. To support these provisions, actions should also be aligned with the principles of ‘recognition of time away from research’ detailed in Chapter 2.

Recommendations

- RFOs and RPOs should work jointly to enable and advocate contractual or legal social security as a requirement for all research professionals, adjusted according to relevant national standards and individual status.
 - RFOs and RPOs should actively engage with national authorities and European institutions to advocate greater alignment of social security provisions, recognising that many of these elements fall within national and EU legislative competences.
- Clear and transparent processes and guidance should be offered by RFOs and RPOs to research professionals they fund or employ regarding the social security provisions available to them.
- Paid leave should have a common legal status across the European Research Area, and Member States, RFOs, and RPOs should work jointly and strive towards a common minimum level of percentage pay.
- RFOs and RPOs should advocate and work jointly towards the implementation of a common and evidence-based European approach to a minimum duration for all forms of parental/ family leave.

Guiding Practices

RESAVER Pension Fund is a pan-European pension solution for research organisations and their employees.

resaver

The **Health Research Board Ireland’s policy on payments of social benefits** provides details of allowable entitlements and how to apply, including those circumstances where an extension to the duration of a grant term may be required as a result of leave.

HR^B Health Research Board

The **Swiss National Science Foundation’s regulations** allow for extension of the eligibility period for the submission of applications (see section 1.11).

Swiss National Science Foundation

The **Spanish State Research Agency’s regulations** allow for an extension of the eligibility period related to interruptions in the research career and causes for suspension of a grant related to work–life balance (Art. 5, 24).

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CHAPTER TWO

RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT

- Academic Freedom
- Fair and Transparent Career Progression and Funding Allocation Processes
- Recognition of Time Away from Research
- Anti-discrimination Policies

Academic Freedom

All research professionals employed and supported by research organisations must be guaranteed freedom of inquiry, academic independence, and working conditions conducive of good research practice.

Recommendations

- RFOs and RPOs should publicly state and demonstrate their position and actions on guaranteeing academic freedom for all supported research professionals.
- RFOs and RPOs should work together to ensure working conditions for all research professionals are conducive to – and supportive of – the highest standards of ethics and integrity, and good research practice.

Guiding Practices

The European Parliament Panel for the Future of Science and Technology's (STOA) study [Horizon Europe: Protecting academic freedom](#) monitored academic freedom by screening and assessing possible policy options to strengthen and improve implementation of Recital 72 in Horizon Europe (*"to guarantee scientific excellence, and in line with Article 13 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights – the programme should promote respect for academic freedom in all countries benefiting from its funds"*), identifying opportunities and bottlenecks towards implementation, and proposing applicable solutions.

The German Research Foundation's (DFG) [White Paper on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice](#) – Guideline 10: Legal and ethical frameworks, usage rights, states *"researchers adopt a responsible approach to the constitutionally guaranteed freedom of research."*

In its [Performance Agreement and Objectives Government for 2026–2030](#), the French National Research Agency (ANR) states *"the Agency remains the central player in project-based funding built on academic freedom, scientific excellence and curiosity-driven research."* As part of its commitment to contributing to the deployment of a supportive framework for conducting research with integrity and responsibility, the ANR principles and procedures are set out in a document entitled [ANR policies on Ethic, Scientific Integrity and Deontology](#), intended for all research stakeholders.

Fair and Transparent Career Progression and Funding Allocation Processes

All career advancement mechanisms implemented by research organisations (including grant allocations) should be open, transparent, merit-based, and inclusive; they should be aligned with the Open, Transparent, and Merit-based Recruitment of Researchers (OTM-R Principles), and informed by the ongoing research assessment reform movement (including the CoARA Commitments).

Recommendations

- RPOs should make all processes and criteria used for recruitment and promotion processes openly available to prospective applicants. RFOs should transparently and openly provide information on the assessment processes and criteria used in funding allocation exercises, as well as information on decision-making bodies and processes.
- All assessment-related processes should be fully aligned to the state of the art in the reform of research assessment movement.
 - RFOs and RPOs should consider joining, actively contributing to, and publicly showing their commitment to ongoing international efforts to reform research assessment, including the principles and commitments set out by CoARA.
- RFOs and RPOs should rigorously implement clear and transparent conflict of interest rules for all funding allocation and career progression exercises.
- Funding allocation and career progression decisions implemented by RFOs and RPOs should be made according to clear merit-based principles, and all external peer review experts and panel members should be provided guidance and training to enable these processes accordingly.
 - RFOs and RPOs should ensure that all evaluators, reviewers, and panel members receive mandatory training on unconscious bias, inclusive assessment practices, and the responsible use of metrics.
 - RFOs and RPOs should ensure gender-balanced, diverse, and multidisciplinary review panels and committees, reflecting the diversity of the research community.
- RFOs and RPOs should have clear policies and procedures for appeals and rebuttal mechanisms, and should provide all applicants, successful or not, with feedback that explains the basis for the outcome.

Guiding Practices

Recognition of Time Away from Research

Eligible and justified breaks from research should have no adverse impacts on career progression, funding eligibility, or research assessments, and relevant skills gained from experience outside of academia should be recognised and rewarded. The reintegration of research professionals following time away from research to e.g., innovation, policy, or other activities should be more actively promoted and recognised.

Recommendations

- A common European approach to eligible periods away from research, and their consideration in all assessment processes, should be co-developed by member states, RFOs, and RPOs.
 - RFOs should ensure that any periods away from research are considered and evaluated fairly in research assessment processes.
 - RPOs should have clear and accessible guidance on how time away from academia is treated in career progression exercises.
- RFOs and RPOs should consider resources or dedicated programmes aimed at helping talented researchers resume research activity after a period away from research.

Guiding Practices

The Health Research Board (HRB) Ireland asks for breaks in research in **Narrative-like CVs** and provides clear guidance to reviewers that these should be taken in consideration when assessing the track record of researchers, e.g. academic age.

The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) **net academic age calculation** allows applicants to be evaluated on their track record of academic achievements according to the time spent working in research.

Introduced in 2022, the use of the **CV template** is now mandatory when applying to the German Research Foundation (DFG). In addition to the mandatory information required in order to assess eligibility, applicants may also provide details of special circumstances or additional services to scholarship. Reviewers are instructed to consider applicants' academic performance in the context of their individual curriculum vitae and career stage.

The **Royal Society (UK) Research Grant** is aimed at researchers at an early stage in their career or returning from a career break and want to purchase specialised equipment and consumables.

Anti-discrimination Policies

All research professionals should be supported and enabled to pursue available career pathways based on individual merits without any form of bias (conscious, unconscious, or systemic), discrimination, or unfair treatment.

Recommendations

- RFOs and RPOs should establish clear anti-discrimination principles and policies and/or codes of conduct across all relevant processes, in line with their national regulations and guidelines.
- RFOs and RPOs should provide clear and accessible reporting and guidance on how they combat potential discrimination in their processes and policies.
- RFOs and RPOs should periodically monitor and review their career support and provision mechanisms for potential forms of bias, discrimination, or unfair treatment.

Guiding Practices

UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) [Action Plan on dignity, respect and anti-bullying, harassment and discrimination.](#)

The [Initiative for Gender Equity in the Public Sector](#) in the US conducts evidence-based research to make public service and public policy more equitable for all gender identities.

The German Research Foundation (DFG) offers a [package of anti-bias measures and support materials.](#)

The French National Research Agency (ANR) [Gender Equality Plan](#) integrates gender equality within research schemes including calls for proposals open to all and project evaluation without gender bias. After an awareness-raising campaign over two editions of the generic calls, the ANR has asked, since 2022, whenever it is relevant, to consider the sex/gender dimension within the research project submitted. The main goal is to avoid any gender biases in the knowledge production and to anticipate the possible consequences, notably health and social ones, of the application of research results.

CHAPTER THREE

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT, WELL-BEING, AND SUPPORTING INFRASTRUCTURE

- Continuous Professional Development
- Work–Life Integration
- Access to Infrastructure and Equipment

Continuous Professional Development

Research professionals should be offered resources and support for training related to skills and competencies relevant to modern research, promoting life-long learning for all, enabling and supporting career progression relevant to academia and beyond.

Recommendations

- A common ERA approach to Career Development Plans, including a common template, should be implemented by RFOs and RPOs, promoting the interoperability of career development processes as research professionals advance and move.
- RFOs and RPOs should ensure protected time, dedicated resources, and formal recognition of professional learning during all periods of funding and employment.
- Supervision, professional support, and mentoring play a critical role in researchers' professional development and should be fully acknowledged and supported.
 - RPOs should provide guidance on and encourage the integration of professional development discussions into supervision and mentoring practices.
 - RFOs should acknowledge and, where relevant, recognise the value of supervisory and mentoring roles taken on by researchers that they fund.
- RPOs ensure a dedicated budget is committed to career development support and training provision, made available to all research professionals. RFOs recognise and incentivise engagement by research professionals in relevant training and career development activities and should provide ring-fenced funding as part of relevant grant schemes for these activities, where possible.

Guiding Practices

European Research Council Executive Agency [Career Development Plan Template](#).

The [EURAXESS Career Handbook for Young Researchers](#) offers a practical guide to help researchers plan their careers, explore opportunities and develop essential skills.

The [European Competence Framework for Researchers](#) is a tool that helps researchers assess and develop their own transversal skills, and institutions and training providers adapt their offer to researchers.

The [Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Guidelines on Supervision](#) constitute a set of recommendations for participant researchers and institutions to ensure the provision of adequate supervision or mentoring and appropriate career guidance.

The [Austrian Science Fund \(FWF\) funding contracts](#) will require the Principal Investigator of a project to allocate sufficient time and resources (ca. 20%) to post-doctoral researchers to develop their own work, ideas, and academic profile, promoting independent scientific development.

Work–Life Integration

Working environments and cultures that enable a healthy work–life balance should be fostered and prioritised by research organisations as fundamental to the attractiveness, productivity, and sustainability careers in research, and the quality and impact of research.

Recommendations

- RFOs and RPOs should work together to jointly ensure that work–life balance provisions are provided to all research professionals, including policies that prevent excessive workloads and/or working hours.
- RPOs should provide flexible working arrangements (including hybrid or remote options) wherever possible without penalising career progression, especially given the need to provide care across generations, for both children and elderly family members.
- RFOs and RPOs should establish monitoring mechanisms to evaluate the implementation and effectiveness of work–life balance measures, including researcher satisfaction surveys and workload indicators.
- RFOs and RPOs should facilitate and encourage the training of supervisors and mentors to promote a culture of respect for personal time, well-being, and mental health.

Guiding Practices

The [Instituto de Medicina Molecular João Lobo Antunes Gender Equality Plan](#) lists measures to promote a healthy work–life balance.

The [Spanish State Research Agency Gender Equality Plan](#) lists measures to monitor, evaluate, and promote a healthy work–life balance.

Access to Infrastructure and Equipment

Research professionals should be provided with the necessary access to facilities, services, and resources to carry out their research activities. Research organisations should simplify and facilitate this access, or support access indirectly if facilities or resources are not available at the host institution, region, or country.

Recommendations

- The facilities, resources, and services available to the research community should be transparently communicated, and guidance on access mechanisms should be provided. Where needed, training and/or specialist support should be available to research professionals alongside access.
 - RFOs, RPOs, and infrastructure organisations should work jointly to improve the visibility, accessibility, and usability of the infrastructure made available to those they fund, employ, and/or support.
 - RFOs should integrate infrastructure and equipment needs into all relevant application processes, and RPOs should encourage the consideration of access requirements during hiring and promotion exercises.

Guiding Practices

The Health Research Board (HRB) Ireland **requests applicants** to describe the infrastructure, facilities, specialist expertise and other support available at the Host Institution and/or at other sites where the research will be conducted. Additionally, HRB requests a description regarding access to research infrastructure, and an infrastructure agreement form must be submitted with the application. Funding for equipment is typically an eligible cost.

Through its **strong integration in international research infrastructures and collaborations**, the Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN) enables high levels of geographical and inter-institutional mobility, allowing researchers and technical staff to engage in long-term placements and collaborative work across Europe and globally.

Conclusions & Next Steps

The recommendations presented here by Science Europe represent a significant step forward in our collective commitment to building a research ecosystem that is attractive and responds to the needs of the talent it seeks to create, attract, and retain.

Across three interconnected domains: Working Conditions and Employment; Research Environment; and, Professional Development, Well-being, and Supporting Infrastructure, this framework of recommendations articulates a shared understanding among Science Europe Member Organisations, both research funding and performing organisations, that a common approach to minimum standards is an important foundation for continued action and advocacy. When research professionals are supported by fair salaries, protected by robust social security provisions, empowered through transparent career pathways, and enabled to integrate their professional and personal lives, they are better positioned to advance our collective knowledge and produce excellent and impactful research.

The good practice examples provided alongside our recommendations demonstrate that progress is already underway across the European Research Area. However, good practice that remains siloed is insufficient. It is imperative to move from isolated practices to systemic change in key areas. This requires not only individual organisational action, but structured co-ordination, collaborative support, and sustained advocacy at all levels of the research system, including towards national governments and European institutions. Priority areas for urgent action include improving contractual stability, strengthening social security provisions, advancing reform of research assessment systems, and enhancing transparency in career progression and funding processes. Science Europe is committed to addressing these challenges, supporting co-ordination and advocacy efforts towards ensuring that these recommendations translate into meaningful improvements to the daily working lives of research professionals across Europe and beyond.

Moving forward, Science Europe commits to supporting its Member Organisations, both individually and collectively, in actions to address the recommendations made. Acknowledging that, in some cases, action is dependent upon and limited by national and European legislation, Science Europe also commits to strong and consistent advocacy based upon the principles highlighted in this publication, supporting members in their respective advocacy and engagement activities.

Finally, this publication is about the human foundations of high-quality research and innovation. Science Europe commits to working with research communities and key community stakeholder voices to collect insights and data upon which further informed policy and practice adaptations can be based. Focus will be given to the needs and expectations of research professionals, particularly early-career researchers as the next generation of leaders that will be funded and employed by Science Europe Member Organisations.

Science Europe AISBL

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Science Europe is the association of major research funding and research performing organisations in Europe.

Our vision is for the European Research Area to have the optimal conditions to support robust education and research & innovation systems.

We define long-term perspectives for European research and champion best-practice approaches that enable high-quality research for knowledge advancement and the needs of society.

We are uniquely placed to lead advancements to the European Research Area and inform global developments through participation in research initiatives where science is a strong and trusted component of sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

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